

ORGANIZATION OF A COMPREHENSIVE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PHYSICS – A DEMAND OF THE TIME

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Abstract. *It is shown that under the credit technology of education in higher education, the problem of training specialists in the field of physics is determined by the radical modernization of academic activities and the development of close and mutually beneficial cooperation between education and the scientific and production spheres.*

Keywords: *improvement, physics education, academic activity, personnel consumers, curriculum.*

Introduction

The introduction of the credit system of education and quality control of students' knowledge (hereinafter – CSE), including in the field of physics, into the educational environment of Uzbekistan became possible under the conditions of widespread computerization of all spheres of socio-economic life. This system required a radical modernization and improvement of the educational process, the renewal of educational-methodical and didactic support, taking into account the specifics of physics education and modern scientific and technical trends [1].

The training of bachelors in physics in the international educational space of developed countries demonstrates the high efficiency of the credit system of education and quality control of students' knowledge [2-5]. This is due to the following factors:

- systematic attention of the heads of universities, research centers and industrial corporations to the key tasks of training specialists in the field of physics;
- constant motivation of the teaching staff and students from enterprises and scientific organizations – consumers of personnel;
- active participation of production associations and research laboratories in the competitive selection of physics graduates;
- academic and organizational freedom of scientific and production structures, contributing to the integration of science, education and production.

The introduction of the CSE in the field of physics involves the organization of a comprehensive educational process, where priority is given to the interaction of universities not only with state bodies managing education, but also with specialized scientific and production associations and research institutes, which are the main consumers of graduates.

Table 1. Main components of the credit system in physics education

Component	Description	Application in Physics
Modular structure	Division of the program into separate modules	Separate modules in mechanics, optics, electrodynamics
Credits (ECTS)	Credit units for mastering a module	Laboratory work in quantum physics

Individual trajectory	Possibility to choose disciplines	Choice of special courses in nuclear physics and materials science
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Thus, solving the problem of training highly qualified specialists in physics has a dual orientation: on the one hand, it is necessary to modernize the academic activities of the departments of physics, and on the other – to develop stable and mutually beneficial cooperation between educational institutions and the scientific and production sector [6-10].

The teaching staff of the departments of physics is able to promptly revise and modernize curricula and programs, focusing on the requirements of a comprehensive educational process [11]. It is important to review the content of disciplines taking into account the opinion of employers: each topic should include both traditional fundamental knowledge in physics and practical recommendations for their application in scientific research, engineering developments and production tasks.

According to the Order of the Minister of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 26, 2018, “On the approval of the Regulation on the system of monitoring and assessing students’ knowledge in higher education institutions”, the criteria for assessing students’ knowledge are defined. In particular:

For the grade “5” (excellent) – the student is required to draw independent conclusions and make decisions, think creatively, conduct independent reasoning, apply acquired knowledge in practice, understand the essence of the subject, and have a general conception of the discipline.

For the grade “4” (good) – students should be able to reason independently, apply their knowledge in practice, understand the essence of the subject, and have a general conception of the discipline.

For the grade “3” (satisfactory) – students are expected to be able to apply their knowledge in practice, understand the essence of the subject, and have a general conception of the discipline.

Thus, in this regulation it is clearly stated that in order to obtain any positive assessment, the main requirement is that students must be able to apply their knowledge in practice.

Taking this into account, in physics classes we organized students’ lecture, practical, laboratory, and independent learning assignments based on the requirements of employers. For example, in laboratory classes, students are given independent learning tasks such as “creating a new virtual laboratory experiment using the PhET pedagogical software tool.” In this assignment, students install the PhET software on their computers, thoroughly familiarize themselves with all available experiments, then select a laboratory activity that is convenient for them and complete the given tasks. As a result, students develop not only the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, but also acquire skills in designing new laboratory activities, creative thinking, and independent use of technical tools.

“We present some examples of laboratory works developed as independent learning assignments for students.”

Determining the Acceleration of Free Fall Using a Mathematical Pendulum – Instruction

1. The program is opened using the Explorer browser.

The length of the mathematical pendulum (Length1) is selected by adjusting the parameter, and the initial length l of the pendulum is measured using the ruler provided in the program.

Using the cursor (as shown in the figure), the deflection angle of the mathematical pendulum must be kept small (not more than 10° – 12°). The pendulum is set into oscillatory motion, and the time taken for 50 oscillations (t) is measured on the screen (indicated by the green circle in the figure). When the pendulum is released into oscillation, the timer must be started. The number of oscillations is counted by the student.

The string is further lengthened, and a new value of l is measured. The measurements described in step 3 are then repeated. Such measurements should be carried out for pendulum lengths corresponding to values in the range of 0.8–1.0 m.

The experiments are performed with a load of mass 1 kg. The mass of the load is selected using the cursor located inside the yellow circle shown in the figure.

The measurement results are recorded in the following table. O'lchash natijalari quyidagi jadvalga yoziladi.

Tajriba tartib raqami	l_0 m	N	t s	$T=t/N$ s	g m/s^2	$\varepsilon(g)$ %
1.		50				
2.						
3.						
4.						
5.						

As the second experiment, we will study the refraction of light and determine the refractive index of the second medium with respect to the first medium.

Using the above link, open the “Refraction of Light” simulation in PhET.

Click “Intro” (Начало) to start.

Select “Air” as the medium through which light is incident, and select “Glass” as the medium in which light is refracted (see Fig. 2).

Record the refractive index of glass n_2 in Table 1.

Take the protractor and set the laser so that the angle of incidence is $\alpha=30^\circ$. Reminder: angles of incidence are always measured from the normal.

Using the protractor, determine the angle of refraction γ for the laser beam and enter it in Table 1. Ignore the reflected ray. (see Fig. 2)

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Repeat the procedure for five additional, different angles of incidence (Steps 2–3), Enter all results in Table 1.

Table 1. Measurement results for refraction of light

N_0	Refractive index n	$\alpha(^{\circ})$	$\gamma(^{\circ})$	$\text{Sin}\alpha$	$\text{Sin}\gamma$	n_2

1						
2						
3						
4						
5						

Table. Examples of Laboratory Works for Independent Learning Assignments

№	Title of Laboratory Work	Objective	Tool Simulation	Tasks for Students
1	Ohm's Law Virtual Experiment	To study the relationship between current, voltage, and resistance.	PhET "Ohm's Law" simulation	– Vary the values of voltage and resistance. – Record the current readings. – Plot the I–V curve. – Conclude about the linear dependence of current on voltage.
2	Projectile Motion Laboratory Work	To analyze the trajectory of a projectile depending on initial velocity/angle.	PhET "Projectile Motion" simulation	– Launch projectiles at 30°, 45°, 60°. – Measure the range and maximum height. – Compare with theoretical values. – Identify the optimal angle for maximum range.
3	Photoelectric Effect Experiment	To investigate the photocurrent dependence on light intensity and frequency.	PhET "Photoelectric Effect" simulation	– Shine light of different frequencies. – Record emission or no emission. – Determine threshold frequency. – Explain results based on quantum theory.

The successful implementation of updated curricula is possible only with coordinated actions of the university administration and enterprises interested in training specialists in physics. Such synergy is the key to the sustainable development of the entire system of personnel training in the field of natural sciences.

However, in a number of countries, the introduction of the CSE has not yielded the expected results due to the lack of partnership relations between universities and scientific and production enterprises, as well as the weak development of the regulatory and legal framework governing such interaction.

A specific feature of the CSE in physics education is the focus on individual educational trajectories of students, the development of skills for independent acquisition and application of knowledge, as well as the earliest possible involvement of students in research projects, internships and practices in production.

Conclusion

From the first days of study, a bachelor in physics should have the opportunity to immerse himself in a comprehensive educational process, including fundamental theory, experimental practice, mastering scientific equipment and software packages for data processing. This is possible only with well-established cooperation between the university and production.

Overcoming barriers to such an educational process is impossible solely by the efforts of teachers using old methodological approaches. It is necessary to revise the entire educational policy, create new curricula and programs that will ensure close and productive connections between science, education and production in the field of physics.

In a number of educational programs, steps have already been taken in this direction: the number of industrial practices has been increased, some classes are held on the basis of research laboratories and design bureaus, and ties with scientific centers and high-tech enterprises are being strengthened. This is especially effective in the training of future physics teachers, where there is an acute shortage of qualified personnel.

These measures form the basis for the sustainable development of human resources in physics and allow timely responses to the challenges of the time by integrating education and science into a single complex.

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